

Gravitational Search Algorithm (GSA) Optimized SSSC Based Facts Controller to Improve Power System Oscillation Stability

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Abstract : The health and environmental risk of eating mushrooms grown in the suburbs of Abakaliki were evaluated in terms of heavy metals accumulation. Mushroom samples were collected from four different farms located at Izzi, Amajim, Amana and Amudo and analyzed for (iron, Fe; lead, Pb; manganese, Mn and cadmium, Cd) using Bulk Scientific Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer 205. Results indicates mean range of concentrations of the trace metals in the mushrooms were Fe (0.22-152.03), Mn (0.74-9.76), Pb (0.01-0.80), Cd (0.61-0.82) mg/L respectively. Accumulation of Cd on the four locations under investigation was higher than the UK Government Food Science Surveillance and World Health Organization (WHO) maximum recommended levels in mushroom for human consumption. The Fe and Mn contaminants of Amudo were significant and show the impact of anthropogenic and atmospheric pollution. The potential sources of the heavy metals in the mushrooms were from urban waste, deposition of dust caused by mining and quarrying activities (air borne dust), natural geochemistry of the area and use of inorganic fertilizers.

Keywords : Heavy metal, mushroom, edible, *Agaricus campestris*, health implication.

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